

Health Community Lab "New Skills for Healthcare Professionals. The Case of the Hospital School"

REPORT

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Progetto: PNRR THE - Tuscany Health Ecosystem

Ambito: Spoke 10 - Population Health, Subproject 4 - Dalla Ricerca all'Impresa

Finanziamento: Unione europea - Next Generation EU

CUP:

Data: [mese e anno di pubblicazione]

Ringraziamenti

Heartfelt thanks are extended to the Meyer University Hospital, the Regional Education Office for Tuscany, and the Andrea Bocelli Foundation. Their participation in our implemented activities and their support for scientific research—formally established through specific agreements and conventions—has been essential to the exploration of education's role in healthcare.

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This document seeks to use inclusive language that respects gender differences. However, when it was not possible to find a stylistically appropriate neutral formulation, the masculine form was used, in accordance with traditional Italian linguistic conventions.

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Executive Summary

This report illustrates the activities and results of the Health Community Lab (HCL) 'School in Hospital' (*La Scuola in Ospedale*), a research, training, and intervention framework developed within Spoke 10 'Population Health' of the Tuscany Health Ecosystem (THE) – PNRR.

The initiative was established to address the need to move beyond a sectoral conception of pedagogy in healthcare settings, thereby promoting a systematic integration of the educational dimension within the continuum of pediatric care. In a context where care is increasingly oriented towards a holistic bio-psycho-social approach, the project aimed to foster new competencies for professionals, supporting the strategic relationship between hospital, school, family, and the local community.

The adopted methodology was rooted in an action research and co-creation approach (Living Lab), actively involving key stakeholders such as the University of Florence (FORLILPSI), the Meyer University Hospital (AOU Meyer), the Regional School Office for Tuscany, and the Andrea Bocelli Foundation.

The HCL involved the design and delivery of three editions (2023–2025) of the Post-Graduate Advanced Course 'School in Hospital,' which trained 81 professionals and 25 university students.

The main findings, derived from an analysis that integrated quantitative methods (questionnaires based on ANVUR TECO-D frameworks) and qualitative methods (ethnographic observation, questionnaire comments, narrative, and autobiographical analyses), demonstrate an exceptionally high and consistently growing level of participant satisfaction. More importantly, the qualitative analysis validated the model as a transformative learning experience, capable of generating a 'shift in perspective' (*cambiamento di sguardo*) and a concrete impact on daily professional practices.

The project has empirically validated an effective training model and served as a social innovation laboratory, consolidating a community of reflective practice and demonstrating pedagogy's strategic role in the humanization of care. The primary added value lies in triggering an empowerment process and establishing the groundwork for the course's evolution into a First-Level University Master's program starting from the academic year 2025–2026, thereby systematizing an advanced training pathway for defining the professional profile and associated competencies of a care professional."

Key Messages

1. Spoke Objective – Prototype

- To build a training model for integrated care.

A certified advanced training pathway (a Advanced Course evolving into a Master's program) has been designed, tested, and validated. This pathway establishes a pipeline of professionals with advanced pedagogical expertise. The model demonstrates that education and training are strategic and necessary processes to enhance the effectiveness of medical and healthcare provision by supporting the coordination among hospital, school, family, and the local community.

2. Spoke Objective – Community Engagement

- To create strategic synergies and networks.

The HCL acted as a catalyst, strengthening multi-stakeholder collaboration (University, Healthcare, School, Third Sector) through co-design and the dissemination of an educational care culture. Synergies were created at both national and international levels, positioning the model as a benchmark and fostering an academic and professional network dedicated to hospital pedagogy.

3. Spoke Objective – Towards an Integrated Care System

- To support actors within the school and educational system.

The training pathway provided teachers, educators, and healthcare operators with concrete tools to improve relational processes in complex care settings. By promoting multi-professional reflective models (e.g., autobiographical practices), the project served as a leverage point for the growth of integrated services, supporting the well-being of professionals and their capacity to act as change agents within their organizations.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Description and Objectives

The Health Community Lab (HCL) “School in Hospital” (“La Scuola in Ospedale”) is configured as a research, training, and intervention framework aimed at promoting the systematic integration of the pedagogical-educational dimension within the continuum of pediatric care.

The Tuscany Health Ecosystem and the Health Community Lab

The *Tuscany Health Ecosystem (THE)* is a research project promoted **by the Tuscany Region and all Tuscan universities**, including the University of Florence, funded by the MUR (Ministry of University and Research) through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR funded by the European Union - Next Generation EU, Mission 4, Component 2, CUP B83C22003920001). THE has been **divided into 10 macro research themes**, assigned to the spokes, all related to life sciences issues. In particular, spoke 10 has been named 'Population Health'. The universities and public and private bodies participating in spoke 10 (Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, University of Florence, University of Pisa, University of Siena, University for Foreigners of Siena, Dedalus spa) aimed to **integrate methods and tools to improve the ability to implement the innovations that will be introduced in the coming years in our health service**, especially through the involvement of the population and the community.

The Department of Economics and Management (DISEI), together with the Department of Architecture (DIDA), the Department of Education, Languages, Intercultural Studies, Literature and Psychology (FORLILPSI), and the Department of Health Sciences (DSS), conducted research in the field of '*Community engagement and social innovation for health and well-being of individuals and territories*', developing the **Health Community Lab (HCL)** methodology, i.e. a collaborative space involving citizens, institutions, businesses and universities to **co-create innovative solutions dedicated to the health and well-being of a community or territory**. As part of the project, each HCL developed tested the methodology in different contexts (for further information, see Biggeri et al. 2025a and Biggeri et al. 2025b), specifically testing certain parts of the process. The HCLs have therefore made it possible to **verify and refine the methodology through concrete cases**, even though these are **partial applications**, limited to specific areas, problems or topics of intervention.

This contribution analyzes the educational co-design process carried out within this HCL, which represents the evolution of a multi-year collaboration model, first formalized in 2015 through an agreement between the Meyer University Hospital (Azienda Ospedaliero-Universitaria, AOU) and the Department of Education and Psychology of the University of Florence (Boffo, 2022).

The project is part of the broader Tuscany Health Ecosystem (THE) research program, funded by the European Union under the Next Generation EU – National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP), specifically within Spoke 10. The scientific and organizational

coordination of the HCL is entrusted to the Department of Education, Languages, Intercultural Studies, Literature, and Psychology (FORLILPSI) of the University of Florence, which has consolidated a strategic synergy with AOU Meyer and the Regional School Office (Ufficio Scolastico Regionale, USR) for Tuscany over the years (Boffo, 2022).

The primary goal of the project is the promotion of a holistic care paradigm, oriented toward protecting the bio-psycho-social well-being of the hospitalized minor and their family unit. This objective is pursued through the development of novel professional profiles and the cultivation of specific competencies, functional to integrating healthcare services with a pedagogical perspective and enhancing network collaboration with the various local stakeholders.

This HCL was realized through the design, implementation, and evaluation of the Post-Graduate Advanced Course "School in Hospital: Training Education, School, and Care Professionals" ("La Scuola in Ospedale. Formare i professionisti dell'educazione, della scuola, della cura"), now in its third edition. The course aims to provide advanced tools for the development of pedagogical-educational and organizational professionalism in pediatric care settings and in collaboration with the local community, utilizing teaching methodologies based on reflective learning (Mezirow, 2016; Schön, 1993) and autobiographical practice (Demetrio, 1996; Boffo & Benelli, 2024).

The main objectives of the Course were directed at:

- Training, through critical-reflective and self-reflective approaches (Siegel & Hartzell, 2005), a qualified professional figure specialized in didactic and educational design to address high-complexity hospital contexts.
- Developing narrative-educational competencies (Cambi, 2002), both diagnostic and prognostic, in professionals from public and private sectors, with particular reference to the educational and healthcare fields, with the aim of increasing the overall well-being of the different operational contexts.

In a perspective of increasing professionalization and training sustainability, and in response to a specific request from the participants, the Advanced Course will evolve into a First-Level University Master's program commencing in the academic year 2025–2026.

Project Component	Specific objectives	Methodology and Tools	Stakeholders involved	Key Results / Products
General Project Framework	To integrate the pedagogical dimension into the continuum of pediatric care. To develop new professional profiles and competencies to bridge healthcare and the local community. To promote a holistic approach to the bio-psycho-social well-being of the minor	Ecological, socio-constructivist, and critical-transformative approach. Mixed Methods Research (MMR) combining qualitative and quantitative inquiry. Living Lab paradigm based on open innovation and co-creation.	FORLILPSI Department (University of Florence), AOU Meyer, Regional School Office for Tuscany, Andrea Bocelli Foundation. Beneficiaries: Healthcare and education professionals,	Creation of a multi-stakeholder collaboration model; Development of a pedagogical training model; Impulse for national and international synergies in the field of hospital pedagogy.

	and the family.		university students, pediatric patients, and families.	
HCL Advanced Course "School in Hospital"	To train education, school, and care professionals. To provide tools for developing pedagogical professionalism in pediatric settings. To deepen biographical and autobiographical analysis (Lifelong Learning). To acquire design methods for high-complexity contexts.	Approach based on reflective and transformative learning. Blended teaching modality (online lessons and in-person workshops). Tools: E-tivities, co-design workshops, evaluation questionnaires (based on ANVUR Teco-D indicators)..	Providers: University professors (pedagogical, psychological, medical areas). Participants: Teachers of all levels, educators, healthcare professionals, master's students in pedagogy and education.	3 editions of the course delivered (2023–2025). Training of 81 professionals and 25 university students. Development of a validated training model set to evolve into a First-Level Master's program from the A.Y. 2025–2026..

Table 1 - Summary Matrix of the HCL "New Competencies for Care Professionals: The Case of the School in Hospital"

1.2 HCL Structure

The organizational architecture of the HCL is founded on a multi-stakeholder collaboration model that, consistent with the Quadruple Helix paradigm (Etzkowitz and Leydesdorff, 2000), actively involves bodies and organizations from the academic sector (University of Florence), healthcare sector (AOU Meyer), institutional-educational sector (Regional School Office for Tuscany), and the non-profit sector (Andrea Bocelli Foundation). This structure, typical of Living Labs, promotes a process of co-creation and open innovation, integrating micro and meso-macro level scientific research with advanced training. The project's governance ensures a systemic approach, partly formalized through specific Memoranda of Understanding that regulate its activities.

HCL phase	Prototype creation activities	Actors involved			
		Public actors	Private actors	Research bodies	Civil society
Preliminary phase	Conception	x	x	x	x
	Context analysis and planning	x	x	x	

<i>Implementati on statement</i>	Design	x	x	x	
<i>Evaluation phase</i>	Distribution/ Dissemination	x	x	x	
	Evaluation	x	x	x	x
	Maintenance	x	x	x	x

Tabella 2 - stakeholder coinvolti nelle fasi dell'Health Community Lab (elab da Larisz et al. 2023).

Stakeholder Category	Specific actor	Role in the project
University and Research	Università degli Studi di Firenze (Dipartimento FORLILPSI)	Holds responsibility for scientific and didactic design, direction of the Advanced Course and PhD program, and research, evaluation, and dissemination activities.
Healthcare	Azienda Ospedaliero-Universitaria (AOU) Meyer	Constitutes the main operational context, co-design partner, and location for workshops and internships. Its "Family Center" serves as a contact point for care continuity and family support.
	AOU Pisa e AOU Siena	Entities involved in collaborative initiatives for in-depth analysis and sharing of best practices and organizational models related to schools in hospital.
	Fondazione Policlinico Universitario Agostino Gemelli IRCCS	Strategic partner in dissemination and discussion initiatives at the national level.
School Institutions	Regional School Office (USR) for Tuscany	Key institutional partner for co-organizing events, promoting the training program, and directing the school in hospital.

	Regional Hub Schools (Infant, Primary, Secondary I and II Grade)	Their respective directors participated in awareness and dissemination initiatives through seminars and conferences, in addition to being the main institutional references for the School in Hospital in Tuscany.
Third Sector and Foundations	Andrea Bocelli Foundation	Ente filantropico partner che contribuisce allo sviluppo del rapporto tra ospedale, scuola e comunità da una prospettiva educativa.
	Cooperativa Arca	The playroom, inaugurated in 2009 and renamed Ludobiblio in 2017 following tighter integration of reading and library activities with play, is an educational space within AOU Meyer. The cooperative actively participated in the training of course participants.

Table 3 - HCL Stakeholder Summary Matrix

1.3. Target Population

The HCL initiatives are aimed at a heterogeneous target population, primarily including hospital and non-hospital teachers of all levels, alongside educational, psychological, and healthcare professionals.

During its three years of implementation, the Advanced Course saw the participation of 81 professionals (school staff, educators, healthcare professionals, psychologists, administrative staff, and volunteers) and 24 female university students from Master's degree programs in "Primary Education Sciences," "Pedagogical Sciences, Training Management for Sustainable Development" (LM 57/85), and "School Leadership and Pedagogy for Inclusion" (LM 50). These students concurrently or subsequently completed a three-month internship period at AOU Meyer.

The most representative age bracket ranges from 40 to 57 years (50%), while those under 40 constitute 25% of the total. The majority of participants (75%) come from the school system. Only 6 participants out of 81 were male (7.4%). This value, however, indicates an increase in male representation compared to the first edition (2022–2023), which had only one male enrollee among 27 total participants.

The demographic and professional analysis of the Advanced Course participants across the three editions reveals a complex and stratified user base, whose composition not only validates the relevance of the training proposal but also constitutes a qualifying element in itself. The heterogeneity of the classroom group is, in fact, not a random data point but the tangible result of the Health Community Lab's methodological approach, which aims to federate diverse professionals around a core set of pedagogical and care competencies.

Figure 1 - Percentage of Participants Divided by Age.

Despite a clear and significant prevalence of professional figures from the school context, the diversity in roles, sectors of origin, and age groups of the participants outlines an authentic learning ecosystem—a crossroad where knowledge, experiences, and different perspectives meet and dialogue, enriching the learning journey.

Figure 2 - Percentage of Participants Divided by Profession.

This formative microcosm faithfully reflects the project's goal of overcoming the sectorization of educational and healthcare interventions by promoting a culture and a model based on integration.

Aggregated data related to the three analyzed editions (A.Y. 2022–2023, 2023–2024, 2024–2025) indicate that the teaching profession constitutes the fundamental core of the user base, representing approximately two-thirds of the total course participants. Although there is an annual fluctuation in representation (55% in the first edition, 85% in the second, and 60% in the last), the consistent participation of teaching staff can be interpreted as an indicator of a specific and widely diffused training need within the national educational system. This adherence highlights a growing awareness that the teaching function transcends the mere transmission of disciplinary content to incorporate a more complex and

articulated dimension of educational care, which requires advanced relational and pedagogical competencies.

Parallel to this consolidated trend, there is a progressive evolution and diversification of participants. The training pathway attracts not only professionals with consolidated experience but also a growing number of young people in training, particularly students from Master's degree programs in pedagogy and education. This emerging cohort represents a potential pool for the development of the new professional profiles that the Health Community Lab project aims to promote. Their interaction in the classroom with highly experienced senior professionals triggers a productive process of intergenerational learning. This cohabitation of different generations within the same training space generates a highly productive context of mutual learning. The laboratory-based and group didactic activities, central to the course's methodological framework, thus become the privileged space for activating informal mentorship dynamics and negotiating new perspectives, significantly enriching the training experience at both the individual and collective levels.

The participants' age distribution constitutes a second dimension of strategic relevance. With the exception of the participation of Master's students, data from the last two editions (2023–2024 and 2024–2025) show a significant concentration of enrollees in the more mature age brackets, with 70% of participants aged between 45 and 67. This data suggests that the course intercepts an explicit need for lifelong learning among professionals with solid experience, who seek in the program an opportunity for updating, systematizing practices, and critical reflection on their professional actions.

Finally, the participation of professionals from the healthcare sector (8%), psychology (3%), social services (4%), and educational services (8%) assumes strategic value. The presence, albeit minority, of these figures was fundamental in facilitating a dialogue between the healthcare and pedagogical cultures, validating the assumption of the transversality of the relational and care competencies that constitute the core of the course.

2. Context of the Initiative and Preliminary Phase

2.1 Analysis of the Socio-Healthcare Context

The analysis of the socio-healthcare context framing the educational-pedagogical professional role in the pediatric field requires a multilevel approach, capable of integrating the international normative framework, the specificities of national and European models, and the operational dynamics of excellence settings like the Meyer University Hospital (AOU Meyer). This examination is preparatory to understanding the systemic challenges and emerging opportunities that define the scope of action and the configuration of an advanced pedagogical role, understood as a strategic function for promoting holistic care and guaranteeing the continuity of life pathways for children and adolescents with chronic illnesses.

The ethical and legal foundation of any intervention in the pediatric field resides in the international normative framework, whose pillar is the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 1989. This treaty, which boasts the highest number of global ratifications, establishes inalienable principles that guide socio-healthcare policies and practices. Key among these are Article 3, which establishes the best interests of the child as a primary consideration in all decisions concerning them, along with a corpus of articles protecting fundamental and interconnected rights: the right to life and development (Art. 6), the right to health and access to healthcare services (Art. 24), the right to quality education (Arts. 28 and 29), and the right to play (Art. 31). The CRC does not merely state rights but mandates ratifying States to harmonize their regulations and implement concrete measures for their realization, establishing a monitoring mechanism through the UN Committee on the Rights of the Child. This universal framework unequivocally affirms that the care of a sick child cannot be separated from the protection of their growth and learning path, configuring health and education as integrated dimensions of a single right to the person.

At the European level, these principles have been incorporated and further specified through programmatic documents that have progressively humanized the hospital setting. The European Charter for Children in Hospital (1986) represents a pioneering document, urging hospitalization to be considered only as a last resort and ensuring adequate conditions for the child's age, such as admission to pediatric facilities, the constant presence of parents, and access to play and study areas. Following this path is the EACH (European Association for Children in Hospital) Charter of 1993, which serves as the continental reference document, outlining precise recommendations to guide the activities of pediatric hospitals in line with CRC principles. A fundamental contribution also comes from the professional associations of educators, with the HOPE (Hospital Organisation of Pedagogues in Europe) Charter of 2000, developed by teachers, pedagogists, and researchers in the sector. This document, stemming from the practice and reflection of the pedagogical community, not only reaffirms the right to education for hospitalized minors but actively promotes collaboration, the exchange of best practices, and the professionalization of hospital teachers at a European level.

The urgency for rethinking the role of pedagogy in care contexts thus emerges from a profound paradigmatic transition affecting health sciences. The shift away from the traditional biomedical model, focused almost exclusively on the biological dimension of

illness, has given way to a bio-psycho-social approach, which recognizes the interconnection between physical state, psychological well-being, and the person's social context (WHO, 1948). Within this framework, health is no longer defined as the mere absence of disease but as a state of complete well-being that includes the subject's capacity to participate actively in social life and pursue their life project (WHO, 2016).

The Italian landscape in this area is characterized by the strategic objective, sanctioned at the National Health Service (SSN) level, of achieving full integration between hospital and community care, known as hospital-territory care continuity. This need arises from the epidemiological transition towards a greater prevalence of chronic and complex diseases, requiring prolonged and fragmented care pathways across different assistance settings. To overcome this fragmentation, the system promotes tools such as Diagnostic-Therapeutic Assistance Pathways (PDTA), integrated clinical networks, and "intermediate care." In this context, the Tuscany Region has implemented a specific model through the establishment of the Hospital-Territory Continuity Agencies (ACOT), multi-professional teams that work to manage complex discharges, coordinating access to the most appropriate care setting. Within this healthcare system, the right to education for sick minors is guaranteed through the School in Hospital (SIO) service and Home Education (ID). The SIO, originating from episodic experiences and progressively institutionalized, is now a service that served almost 60,000 students in 257 hospital sections in 2024/2025. The management and coordination of the service are entrusted to a Network of 19 regional hub schools, tasked with sharing best practices, promoting training, and liaising with the Ministry and Regional School Offices (USR) to ensure uniformity and effectiveness of the service.

The case study of the AOU Meyer in Florence allows for an in-depth analysis of the implementation of these principles in a context of excellence. Meyer has translated the philosophy of holistic care and family centrality into concrete structures and services. An emblematic example is the "Anna Meyer" Family Center, an innovative structure that serves as a focal point for reception, care continuity, psychological and social support, linguistic-cultural mediation, hospitality, and public relations. The Family Center integrates fundamental services, placing the family at the center of the care process from the very first moment and overcoming the fragmentation of the reception experience. The Hospital-Territory Care Continuity Service (UCOT) operates within it, acting as the strategic interface between the hospital and the territory, managing information sharing, coordinating care, organizing multi-professional meetings, and promoting caregiver training for home management.

The contemporary healthcare model, as also outlined by the NRRP, is shifting towards "initiative healthcare" or "proximity medicine."⁴ This paradigm implies proactive action by professionals, called to intercept people's needs through multi-professional networks and integrated services that ensure continuity of care between hospital and territory. This evolution transforms the patient's role from passive recipient to conscious actor of their own health, broadening the very concept of health to include, in addition to the biological dimension, the psychological and social ones.

In this framework, education assumes a strategic added value. Educational competencies become essential for promoting learning, growth, and personal development, fostering empowerment processes aimed at building lasting well-being. The implementation of quality

⁴ Ministerial Decree 71/2022, approved on April 21, 2022, defines the new models and standards for the development of territorial assistance within the National Health Service (SSN) in response to the NRRP (National Recovery and Resilience Plan) guidelines on Health.

systems in the sector has indeed highlighted the need for a holistic approach that integrates the technical competencies of Evidence Based Medicine with the humanistic and relational ones of Medical Humanities and Narrative Based Medicine.

The school in hospital emerges as a paradigmatic example of this synergy. It represents an element of normalization in an exceptional context, acting as a coordination hub among different professional figures and institutions. Its function is not exhausted by the mere provision of a didactic service but is configured as a person-centered care model, creating a bridge between the hospital and the child's context of origin.

2.2 Theoretical Foundations and Literature Review

At the core of this model lies the polysemic construct of "care" (*cura*) (Mortari, 2006; Boffo & Togni, 2023), which the present research assumes as the conceptual crossroad and paradigmatic axis of the pedagogical discourse. The epistemological approach underpinning this action-research project is rooted in a profound re-evaluation of the construct of "care," interpreted no longer as a mere technical-healthcare act or simple assistance service, but as a complex and multidimensional pedagogical category. This perspective, while based on its ancient philosophical matrices—from the Platonic ideal of integral personal formation to Heideggerian existential analytics that places *Sorge* (care) as the fundamental structure of *Dasein* (Being-there)—intends to focus on its more recent and fruitful interpretations within the human, social, and health sciences. The goal of this examination is to argue how "caring for" (*prendersi cura*) constitutes the foundation of authentic educational action, whose systematic implementation is crucial, if not essential, in contexts of high existential vulnerability such as the pediatric hospital (Boffo, 2022).

In such an environment, the condition of illness and the experience of hospitalization do not merely represent a clinical challenge but a profound biographical rupture for the child and their family unit (Demetrio, 1996)—a critical event that interrupts the developmental trajectory and threatens the integrity of the person in their bio-psycho-social totality. It is precisely in this existential gap that pedagogy finds its elective space for intervention, not as an ancillary discipline to medicine, but as strategic knowledge capable of orienting the entire healthcare organization towards an authentically holistic care model.

Contemporary Hospital Pedagogy (PO), moving beyond its original mission of merely guaranteeing didactic continuity, now proposes itself as a frontier discipline, a critical and transformative knowledge that aims to "care for the care environment," promoting relational, organizational, and cultural contexts where every child-patient can continue to feel and be recognized primarily as a growing person, an active subject in their own life and learning journey.

The paradigmatic transition that has affected health sciences in recent decades has progressively eroded the foundations of the traditional biomedical model, centered almost exclusively on the pathology, its etiology, and its pharmacological or surgical treatment. This reductionist approach, which tends to objectify the patient by abstracting them from their life context, has been increasingly countered by the bio-psycho-social model, which recognizes health and illness as the outcome of a complex interaction of biological, psychological, and socio-cultural factors. This holistic vision has opened the door to a profound re-evaluation of the very concept of care. A crucial semantic and conceptual distinction has thus been established, particularly evident in the Italian language, between "curare" (to cure) and "prendersi cura" (to care) (WHO, 1948). While the first term refers to a predominantly

technical, specialized, and restorative action aimed at removing the disease and restoring a condition of physiological normality, the second evokes an existential posture—a global attitude directed at the person in their entirety and unrepeatable uniqueness. "Caring for" is not exhausted by the effectiveness of the healthcare service but is substantiated by the quality of the relationship established between the caregiver and the cared-for. It is an action that implies listening, empathy, responsibility, solicitude, and respect; it is a process that focuses not only on "curing the illness" but on "promoting the well-being" of the person, even when clinical recovery is not possible.

From this solid theoretical foundation, which sanctions the centrality of a holistic and relational approach to health, the specific field of Hospital Pedagogy (PO) develops. Hospital Pedagogy, as a specialized sector of Pedagogy, began its evolutionary journey at the dawn of the 20th century, with its first interventions addressing the needs of minors who were victims of war conflicts, hospitalized in healthcare settings, and frequently orphaned after World War II. At that juncture, the need became apparent for healthcare personnel to go beyond basic assistance services, promoting an integrated approach towards childhood aimed not only at sustenance and medical care but also at educational interventions and the satisfaction of needs such as socialization and the construction of affective bonds.

3. Methodology

3.1. Methodological Framework

The overall methodological framework is rooted in an ecological paradigm (Bronfenbrenner, 2002), combined with socio-constructivist and critical-transformative perspectives (Del Gobbo, 2018). It utilizes an evidence-based research approach that integrates qualitative and quantitative methods, known as Mixed Methods Research (MMR) (Creswell & Clark, 2018). This choice allowed for a more in-depth exploration of the phenomenon's complexity, combining the richness of narrative data with the robustness of numerical data through a triangulation process that strengthened the validity of the results. The foundational methodology driving the entire HCL was action research (Trincherò, 2004)—a cyclical process of planning, action, observation, and reflection—aimed not only at understanding the reality under examination but also at actively improving it in collaboration with the involved stakeholders.

The project aimed to address a specific and widespread training need among school and care professionals: the acquisition of advanced relational, pedagogical, and organizational competencies necessary to operate in high-complexity settings such as pediatric hospitals. The initial inquiry, therefore, was not limited to the educational-pedagogical training of hospital professionals but included the promotion of a culture of integration among the healthcare system, the school system, and the local community, developing novel professional profiles capable of acting as catalysts for this synergy.

The development of a competency model for pedagogical professionalism operating in healthcare requires a multifactorial theoretical framework that integrates the definition of core competencies with reflective and transformative pedagogical approaches.

To ensure methodological rigor in the evaluation and redesign of the course, the national project TECO-D Pedagogy, promoted by ANVUR (2017), was adopted as the reference framework. By defining the core content of the study program through a collaborative and systematic analysis of the textual content of the Annual Single Forms (SUA) from various universities, this initiative provides a validated methodology for identifying the fundamental expected competencies in a graduate. This process led to the definition of six Final Learning Objectives (OFF), articulated into thirty Specific Learning Objectives (OFS) according to the Dublin Descriptors, covering crucial areas such as:

1. Constructs and theories for interpreting educational and training events and developing professional identity.
2. Research methodology and analysis of training needs in social and organizational contexts.
3. Design models in different social and organizational contexts.
4. Relational and situational dynamics in different educational and training contexts.
5. Methods and techniques for the development and facilitation of learning processes.
6. Management of educational and training organizations.

This approach ensures that the training is anchored to a set of shared and recognized learning outcomes, a critical element for building a coherent professional identity in a specialized area like pediatric care.

The model materializes into a pedagogical approach that is simultaneously human-centered and oriented towards reflective and transformative learning. This aligns with the principles of the Health Community Lab guidelines (see Chapter 3), which place the human being at the center of the design process, considering their needs and potential.

The training framework is designed to foster a reflective practice, as conceptualized by Donald Schön (1993), where professionals learn to critically think about their actions (reflection-in-action) and continuously restructure the complex and uncertain situations typical of high-complexity settings. Tools such as e-tivities and the drafting of professional autobiographies, employed in the HCL "School in Hospital," serve as self-reflective learning devices, stimulating participants to analyze their lived experiences and the complexity of interpersonal relationships and the ethics of care. The pathway also promotes transformative learning, according to Jack Mezirow's theory (2016), encouraging participants to critically question their assumptions and meaning perspectives to foster deeper understanding and lasting change in their professional vision and practice. This process aims to develop the essential life skills needed to manage personal and professional transitions and challenges, transforming professionals into social agents capable of continuous reflection on experience. The entire organizational structure falls under the Quadruple Helix paradigm, which guides the collaborative dynamics of the HCL (see Chapter 3). This model postulates that innovation and effective problem-solving can emerge from the dynamic interaction of four key societal actors: academia (universities and research institutions), public institutions (government and health entities), industry (businesses), and civil society (third sector, associations, and citizens). In the context of "The School in Hospital," this translates into a synergistic collaboration among the university (FORLILPSI Department), healthcare institutions (AOU Meyer), the school system (Regional School Office for Tuscany), and the third sector (Andrea Bocelli Foundation). This multi-actor approach ensures that the competency model is not a mere academic exercise but is co-created and validated through continuous dialogue between research, policy, and professional practice. Co-creation is understood as a robust and strong participatory process that facilitates the exchange of ideas, discussion, and collective action, promoting the ownership of solutions and the construction of resilient communities (Betti et al, 2023). In this learning ecosystem, where knowledge is generated and validated through shared action, the creation of a community of learning is fostered, where participants collaborate to acquire new knowledge and skills in an environment of mutual support. The resulting professional profile is thus equipped not only with disciplinary knowledge but also with the transversal competencies necessary to operate effectively within complex organizational ecosystems and contribute to the creation of integrated and truly person-centered care pathways.

What is co-creation?

Co-creation is an approach based on **active collaboration between a plurality of stakeholders** (Vargas et al., 2022), aimed at **the creative resolution of shared problems** (McCaffrey et al., 2025; Messiha et al., 2023). This process develops throughout all stages of the initiative, from the exploration and identification of needs or critical issues to the design, implementation and evaluation of solutions or interventions.

In recent years, co-creation has become increasingly important in the context of strengthening health systems. In its global strategy for integrated health services 2016-2026, the World Health Organisation (WHO) promotes a co-creative process for the development of integrated and people-centred health services through the involvement of governments, service providers and citizens (WHO, 2015). Co-creation therefore plays a central role in this area, as **the challenges faced by contemporary public systems, often characterised by increasing social complexity, require the active involvement of a wide range of social actors in public governance** (Torfing & Ansell, 2021).

What is the difference between co-planning, co-design and co-creation?

Co-programming and co-design (Art. 55, Legislative Decree 11/2017) are structured and regulated forms of public-third sector or public-citizen collaboration, while co-creation is a more recent and broader concept that takes on a wider, horizontal and participatory dimension involving all stakeholders - users, communities, professionals, institutions and research.

- **Co-planning** refers to the phase in which administrations and other actors jointly identify needs, priorities, methods of intervention and resources.
- **Co-design** concerns the following phase, in which the actors involved define and implement specific projects or interventions on the basis of shared planning.
- **Co-creation** goes even further: it involves the participation of all actors from conception, design, implementation and evaluation, with the aim of generating together.

3.2. Research Phases

The research and intervention design characterizing the Health Community Lab (HCL) is therefore founded on a complex and stratified methodological framework. This framework integrates theoretical paradigms, investigative strategies, and training practices into a cyclical and recursive process, aimed not only at the production of new knowledge but also at the transformation of the professional and organizational contexts under investigation. The overall approach is deeply rooted in the paradigm of reflective and transformative learning, as theorized and developed by Donald Schön (1993) and Jack Mezirow (2016). It is substantiated by an eminently human-centered framework that places the needs,

experiences, and perspectives of participants at the core of the process, viewing them not merely as objects of study but as co-researchers and active protagonists of their own training path. The methodology adopted is not a linear and predefined protocol, but a dynamic process that evolved over the three years of the project, constantly informed by data emerging from field research and the monitoring of training activities. This process can be articulated, for explanatory purposes, into a cyclical model composed of four interdependent phases: a preliminary phase of needs and literature analysis, a phase of co-creation and intervention design, a phase of implementation and field experimentation, and finally, a phase of synthesis and continuous evaluation that feeds a new cycle of analysis and redesign.

The first phase, preliminary and analytical in nature, constituted the empirical and theoretical foundation upon which the entire project architecture was built. This initial stage included an in-depth and systematic analysis of the relevant scientific literature, the outcomes of which were detailed in the previous section (cf. Section 2), aimed at mapping the state-of-the-art in hospital pedagogy and identifying the most pertinent theoretical constructs to guide the inquiry.

Figure 3 - Research Phases

Concurrently, a precise analysis of the training needs of care and education professionals operating in pediatric contexts was conducted through the previously illustrated Tecod framework. This analysis was not a one-off action but a recursive process. The very design of the Advanced Course in the 2023–2024 academic year, for example, is the direct result of a program re-modulation based on the analysis of monitoring data collected during the first edition (A.Y. 2022–2023). Participants’ feedback had clearly highlighted the need to reduce the training load, particularly by cutting down the number of in-person meetings to make the course more sustainable for professionals already burdened by intense work commitments. This triangulation of sources—scientific literature, participant feedback, and ethnographic

observation—allowed for the construction of a solid evidence base for training and research design genuinely anchored to the needs of the context.

The second phase, dedicated to co-creation and design, represents the beating heart of the Living Lab approach adopted by the project. Consistent with this paradigm, the design of interventions was not a top-down process imposed by the academic research group but a dialogic and collaborative activity that actively involved all key stakeholders. The definition of the objectives, content, and methodologies of the training pathway, as well as dissemination initiatives, occurred in close synergy with institutional partners, particularly the AOU Meyer, the Regional School Office for Tuscany, and the Andrea Bocelli Foundation. This participatory approach extended even more radically to the course participants themselves, who were constantly considered "actors" in the educational process and protagonists of the research. In response to the monitoring results from the first edition, the second edition (A.Y. 2023/2024) underwent a significant re-modulation of the schedule and content to precisely address the expressed needs. The topics covered, while maintaining a central focus on pedagogy in care contexts, were refined to delve into specific areas of interest.

Furthermore, the learning activity, or E-tivity, proposed at the conclusion of Module IV of the 2024–2025 edition, was developed within a workshop modality. "We Will Lead the Fifth Module!" ("Il quinto modulo lo facciamo noi!") consisted of a simulated co-design experience within the Advanced Course where participants, divided into small groups, were asked to design a hypothetical fifth supplementary module to the content already proposed, thus further improving the training outputs. The dimension of self-reflectivity and autobiography was further stimulated by the research conducted by Prof. AnnaMaria Di Fabio concerning "emotional dimensions in socio-healthcare organizational contexts," which unfolded through the administration of targeted questionnaires in the initial and final phases of the Advanced Course. These questionnaires aimed to read the emotional-motivational component within professional and life paths. The integration of Professor Di Fabio's research within the Advanced Course allowed for the experimentation of an innovative training approach that valued the emotional dimension, promoting the development of transversal competencies such as self-reflection and autobiographical research methodology. The most significant result of the design phase was undoubtedly the co-creation and planning of a First-Level Master's program for the academic year 2025–2026, together with the HCL's institutional partners.

The third phase, that of implementation and experimentation, represents the moment when the design plan translated into concrete action. This phase temporally coincides with the delivery of the three editions of the Advanced Course (held between February and September in the years 2023, 2024, and 2025). The didactic organization of the course was characterized by a blended modality, chosen to combine the advantages of distance learning with the irreplaceable value of in-person interaction. The pathway alternated synchronous online frontal lectures, which allowed the involvement of faculty and participants from different geographical areas and the in-depth study of theoretical content, with experiential in-person workshops, conceived as spaces for practical experimentation, discussion, and the construction of a learning community. The course was structured into four thematic modules, each comprising distance training sessions (usually three) and one intensive in-person workshop. Didactic activities were concentrated on Saturdays to facilitate the participation of working professionals, with a schedule distributed across March, April, May, June, and

September. The in-person workshops took place in significant locations, alternating between the classrooms of the Forlilpsi Department at the University of Florence, to underscore the academic matrix of the course, and the premises of the AOU Meyer, to encourage direct contact with the care context under study. A differentiated attendance requirement (70% for distance meetings, 80% for in-person ones) was established to ensure the continuity and seriousness of the training pathway.

In light of the results from the monitoring and satisfaction evaluation of the first edition of the Advanced Course (A.Y. 2022–2023), which aimed to intercept participants' main needs in itinere, a reduced number of in-person meetings were held along with a re-modulation of the teaching schedule. Specifically, the themes addressed during the edition aimed to:

- Recognize the formative value of didactic strategies centered on the educational relationship that support practices in medical-healthcare care contexts for childhood and adolescence (Baldacci, 2004).
- Deepen biographical and autobiographical analysis from a Lifelong Learning perspective (Federighi, 2000), with particular attention to the adult world, informal education, and Embedded and Transformative Learning.
- Understand the main narratological theories with particular reference to the human and social sciences.
- Acquire methods and techniques for didactic, educational, and pedagogical planning in situations of high ecological-environmental complexity (Hannan & Freeman, 1989; Senge, 1990).
- Utilize, for educational purposes, the main tools of qualitative research in professional contexts (Trincherò, 2004).
- Deepen the systemic and inclusive value of narrative/biographical/autobiographical practices in organizational contexts (Tronto, 1993), with particular reference to places of social, economic, and psycho-physical fragility.

As can be seen from Table 4, the Course was articulated at a multidisciplinary level, involving medical and psychological professionals, while maintaining the prevalence of a specific pedagogical matrix. Four modules were conducted, each comprising 3 distance training sessions and 1 in-person session. The proposed modules aimed to deepen the micro, meso, and macro levels of educational-pedagogical professionalism in pediatric contexts.

MODULES AND COURSES	SSD (Scientific Disciplinary Sector)	CFU (Credits)
Educational, School, and Care Professions: Biographical and Autobiographical Methodologies and Methods		6
The educational relationship in care professions: an adult education theme (Part I)	PAED-01/A	2
Psychology of pediatric illness	PSIC-02/A	1

Narration and autobiographical research	PAED-01/A	2
Narrative Medicine and care for professions	PAED-01/A	1
Educational Relationships and Formative Didactics in School and Healthcare Contexts		6
E-learning and didactics in school and healthcare contexts	PAED-02/A	1
Formative design in school contexts	PAED-01/A	1
Digital and disability	PAED-02/A	1
Relational resources: the relationship between doctors and teachers in hospital contexts	MEDS-20/A	1
Evaluation of school and learning systems	PAED-02/B	1
Biographies and autobiographical practices for learning in school and healthcare contexts	PAED-01/A	1
Ecologies of Organizational Processes in the Healthcare Sector		6
The educational relationship in care professions: an adult education theme (Part II)	PAED-01/A	1
Pedagogy of innovation in healthcare contexts	PAED-01/A	2
Educational ecosystem and system evaluation	PAED-02/B	2
Emotional dimensions in socio-healthcare organizational contexts (Part I)	PSIC-03/B	1
Designing Training in School and Healthcare Contexts		6
The educational relationship in care professions: an adult education theme (Part III)	PAED-01/A	1
Psychology of disability: designing inclusion at school	PSIC-02/A	2
School, community, and health	PAED-01/B	2
Emotional dimensions in socio-healthcare organizational contexts (Part II)	PSIC-03/B	1
Total Frontal Didactics CFU		24
Final Examination		1
Total		25

Table 4: Modules and Courses, 2024/2025 Edition

At the conclusion of each training module, an E-tivity (Electronic Activity) was conducted by all participants, overseen by 4 different instructors involved in the Course delivery. Every E-tivity was conceived and proposed as a tool for self-reflective learning.

The objective of Module I was to lay the theoretical and methodological foundations of the pathway. It aimed to provide participants with a solid understanding of the epistemological foundations of biographical and autobiographical methodologies, equipping them with tools to construct narratives and use life stories as a device for knowledge, intervention, and, critically, reflection on their professional practice and personal experience in relation to caring for others. The concluding E-tivity of this module, consistent with the experiential

approach, required each participant to conceive and produce a curriculum of their professional activity through images, using one of the narration models presented to highlight competencies, knowledge, and skills in a creative and unconventional form, thereby activating a deep self-reflective process.

Module II shifted the focus to practical competencies in managing interpersonal dynamics and didactic planning. The objectives ranged from acquiring skills for the effective management of educational relationships to developing the capacity to design innovative and inclusive didactic interventions, with specific attention to the use of digital technologies for disability and the promotion of interprofessional collaboration among teachers, doctors, and healthcare operators. Central to this module was the reflection on the evaluation of school systems and didactic approaches. The proposed E-tivity required participants to work in groups to identify the competency areas and expected professional behaviors related to the professional standard of well-being—a practical exercise designed to translate a complex theoretical concept into observable indicators applicable to their professional context.

The training pathway comprising Module III aimed to propose an integrated and multidisciplinary vision of the organizational and relational dynamics characterizing the socio-healthcare world. The objective was to provide care professionals with the necessary tools to understand and intervene within and upon organizational processes, promoting a person-centered approach and innovation, including technological and digital. This module introduced the key concepts of organizational ecologies, analyzing the interactions between different actors (patients, operators, institutions) and the environmental factors influencing care processes. Organizational cultures and leadership models within healthcare facilities were explored. The E-tivity proposed in this module involved the drafting of a professional autobiography, following guidelines inspired by scientific-academic methodology.

Finally, the last scheduled Module, Module IV, concentrated on formative design in school and healthcare contexts. It focused on the design of personalized training pathways centered on people's needs and potential, as well as the latest didactic innovations, with particular attention to the utilization of active and collaborative methodologies. The final paper for the training pathway consisted of drafting a scientific poster representing the professional autobiography.

The fourth and final phase, of synthesis and evaluation, is not to be understood as a concluding moment but as a transversal and continuous process that permeated the entire project. The evaluation was conceived in a dual sense: in itinere (ongoing) and final.

At the conclusion of each individual module, a systematic monitoring and evaluation activity was conducted through the administration of anonymous questionnaires to participants. In total, 243 questionnaires related to the 4 different training modules were administered during the three years of the Advanced Course implementation.

The construction of these evaluation instruments was not arbitrary but was based on a solid scientific framework: the evaluation indicators were borrowed and adapted from the national project *Teco-D Pedagogy*, promoted by ANVUR (National Agency for the Evaluation of the University and Research System). The choice of this model guaranteed both methodological rigor and data comparability.

Figure 4 - Description of research phases

The analysis of the results followed a Mixed Methods approach, combining the quantitative processing of numerical data from the questionnaires (e.g., Likert satisfaction scales) with an in-depth qualitative analysis of the open comments left by participants and the products elaborated during the E-tivities. This methodological triangulation allowed for a rich and multidimensional evaluation, capable of capturing not only the level of satisfaction but also the transformative impact of the pathway on the participants' awareness, competencies, and professional practice, while simultaneously providing valuable insights for subsequent project improvement cycles.

3.3 Techniques and Tools

The methodological architecture of the Health Community Lab (HCL) project is substantiated by a multi-faceted and integrated repertoire of investigation techniques and tools, carefully selected in coherence with the reference paradigm of Mixed Methods Research (MMR). The choice of a multi-method approach does not stem from mere eclecticism but from a precise epistemological need: to address the intrinsic complexity of the subject matter—the role of pedagogy in pediatric care contexts—through a plurality of interpretative lenses capable of illuminating its various facets. In line with the principles of methodological triangulation, the synergistic use of quantitative and qualitative tools was aimed at ensuring greater robustness and validity of the results, allowing for the corroboration, deepening, and, at times, challenging of data emerging from each collection channel. This framework allows for overcoming the intrinsic limits of any single approach, combining the breadth and generalizability of numerical data with the depth and contextual richness of narratives and individual experiences. The research and intervention process thus utilized a diversified "methodological toolbox," in which each tool was employed with a specific purpose, contributing to the composition of a complex and multidimensional mosaic of knowledge. Although the project's prevailing orientation is qualitative and exploratory in nature, the quantitative component played a crucial and irreplaceable role, particularly in the systematic monitoring phase of the Advanced Course and the objective evaluation of specific constructs. The principal instrument of this line of inquiry was the structured questionnaire, employed using a logic of continuous (in itinere) and final collection.

The design of the satisfaction and evaluation questionnaires, administered to participants at the end of each training module, was not left to improvisation but was anchored to a solid and validated national scientific framework. The indicators and dimensions of analysis were, in fact, borrowed and adapted from the TECO-D Pedagogy project, promoted by ANVUR (National Agency for the Evaluation of the University and Research System). The choice of this model guaranteed a high level of methodological rigor, aligning the course evaluation with national standards and allowing attention to be focused on six final learning objectives, considered qualifying for the professional profile of the educator and pedagogue. These objectives—which range from mastering constructs and theories for interpreting educational events, to research methodology, from design models to the management of relational dynamics, up to methods for facilitating learning and organizational management—constituted the conceptual grid through which the perceived effectiveness of the training pathway was measured. The administration, carried out via an online platform to ensure anonymity and facilitate completion, allowed for the collection of quantitative data on a large scale, analyzed through procedures of descriptive statistics to map trends, calculate response frequencies, and identify average satisfaction levels relative to each individual course and laboratory activity.

In addition to the evaluative function, the questionnaire was employed as a diagnostic tool. A paradigmatic example is represented by the research on "emotional dimensions in socio-healthcare organizational contexts," integrated into the training pathway. In this case, the administration of specific validated questionnaires in the initial and final stages of the course allowed for measuring the evolution of emotional-motivational constructs in participants, providing quantitative data on the transformative impact of the training experience not only on technical competencies but also on the sphere of self-awareness and emotional management. The quantitative analysis was thus not conceived as an end in itself but as a fundamental link in the project's action research cycle: its results provided a data-driven evidence base for the continuous re-modulation of the training offer, guiding the design choices of subsequent editions and ensuring a process of constant, evidence-based improvement.

The empirical investigation architecture of the Health Community Lab is further represented by the use of an articulated set of qualitative techniques, aimed at deeply exploring the lived experience of professionals, understanding organizational cultures, and bringing out the meanings that actors attribute to their own experience.

Methodological Category	Tool / Technique	Main Purpose	Specific Application in the HCL Project	Products / Data Generated
General Approach	Mixed Methods Research (MMR)	To integrate quantitative and qualitative methods for a holistic understanding and data	Used as the guiding paradigm for the entire research architecture, combining numerical data	A complex, multidimensional analysis ensuring greater robustness and validity of results.

		triangulation.	(questionnaires) with narrative data (autobiographies, posters, comments, participant observation).	
Quantitative Investigation	Structured Questionnaire	To systematically monitor the Advanced Course; To evaluate formative and learning effectiveness related to the TecoD constructs.	Administered online at the end of each course module. Utilized indicators validated by the ANVUR TECO-D Pedagogy project.	Numerical data (satisfaction means, frequencies), descriptive statistical analyses, measurement of transformative impact.
Qualitative Exploration	Participant Observation	To understand and evaluate the dynamics and formative processes triggered by participation in the Advances Course	Conducted during the implementation of the three editions of the Advanced Course (2022-2023, 2023-2024, 2024-2025).	Detailed field notes, ethnographic descriptions, deep and contextualized understanding of the training sessions.
	Narrative and Autobiographical Methods (E-tivity)	1. (Pedagogical): To stimulate reflective learning and the construction of professional identity. 2. (Research): To collect direct data on participants' sensemaking processes.	Proposed at the end of each course module (e.g., visual curriculum, professional autobiography). Products used as research material.	1. Increased awareness of the pedagogical role in healthcare contexts. 2. Corpus of qualitative data for the analysis and definition of competencies for the pedagogical professional.

Action Research / Co-Creation	Co-Design Workshop	To involve stakeholders as partners in design; To enable learning and generate knowledge through action.	Systematically used with institutional partners for course design. Key example: "We Will Lead the Fifth Module!" activity with participants.	New course/project proposals – First-Level Master's Program – qualitative data on training needs, participant empowerment process.
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Table 5 - HCL Methodological Matrix

One of the most immersive and powerful techniques utilized was Participant Observation, conducted during the implementation of the three editions of the Advanced Course (2022-2023, 2023-2024, 2024-2025). This approach, clearly rooted in ethnography, allowed the researcher to "enter" the field of investigation, participating in the daily life of the organization and observing practices, interactions, and routines from within. Through the writing of detailed field notes, it was possible to document not only what actors say they do, but also what they actually do, capturing the tacit, implicit, and non-verbal aspects of the organizational culture. The observation provided a contextualized and profound understanding of the formative dynamics and the corresponding learning responses from participants.

Furthermore, Narrative and Autobiographical Methods played a prominent role. These tools had a dual and synergistic function: on one hand, they were the core of the Course's pedagogical methodology; on the other, they proved to be a valuable source of data for the research. The E-tivities proposed at the end of each module—such as creating a visual curriculum, drafting a professional autobiography, or the simulated design of a new training module—were conceived as reflective learning devices, aimed at stimulating a process of critical analysis of professional identity and practice in the participants. Simultaneously, the products of these activities (the texts, images, projects) were collected and analyzed as qualitative data. The analysis of these documents allowed for direct and unmediated access to participants' sensemaking processes, helping to understand how they integrated course content into their frames of reference and to evaluate the transformative impact of the training experience on their professional vision.

Consistent with the Living Lab approach and the principles of Action Research, the project made extensive use of co-creation practices, aimed at actively involving stakeholders not only as sources of information but as partners in the design and implementation of innovative solutions. The main instrument of this intervention line was the Co-Design Workshop.

This work modality was systematically used in the design and redesign phases of the Advanced Course through operational meetings with representatives from the AOU Meyer, USR Toscana, and the Andrea Bocelli Foundation, ensuring the training pathway's maximum adherence to the real needs of the context. However, the most significant example of this practice is the "We Will Lead the Fifth Module!" activity, already mentioned as a final E-tivity.

This workshop was not merely an exercise but an authentic action-research setting, where the very act of co-designing became an opportunity to generate knowledge. By analyzing the group processes, the proposals elaborated, and the motivations provided by the participants, invaluable data was collected on which content areas to strengthen, which teaching methodologies were most appreciated, and which competencies were considered most urgent to develop from their perspective. In this sense, the co-design workshop blurs the boundaries between training, research, and intervention: it is a device that enables learning, produces data for analysis, and simultaneously triggers a process of empowerment and change, transforming participants into active agents of innovation. The integration of these techniques and tools allowed the Health Community Lab to develop a rigorous yet flexible investigation pathway, capable of adapting to the complexity of reality and pursuing its dual objective: producing valid scientific knowledge and concretely contributing to the improvement of care and education practices.

4. Results of the Co-Creative Phase

4.1 Introduction

The second phase of the Health Community Lab (HCL), dedicated to co-creation and design, represents the operational core of the Living Lab methodological approach adopted by the project. This phase is not an isolated action but a dynamic, dialogic process in which the results from the preliminary analytical phase—literature analysis, participant observation, and mapping of training needs—are translated into targeted training interventions, project prototypes, and research initiatives. Consistent with an eminently human-centered and socio-constructivist paradigm, design was not a top-down process dictated by the academic research group but a collaborative and recursive activity that actively involved all key stakeholders. Within this framework, care and education professionals, institutional partners, and the participants themselves were considered not as mere recipients but as co-researchers and active protagonists, essential actors in defining objectives, modulating content, and experimenting with new practices. The activities undertaken in this phase demonstrate the commitment to overcoming the traditional separation between theory and practice, and between research and intervention, to create an authentic learning ecosystem where knowledge is generated and validated through shared action. The outcomes of this phase, detailed below, should therefore not be understood as finished products but as significant milestones in a constantly evolving action-research cycle that feeds and guides the subsequent implementation and evaluation phases.

4.2 Outcomes of the Co-Creative Phase of the HCL Advanced Course "The School in Hospital. Training Professionals in Education, Schooling, and Care"

4.2.1 Preliminary Phase: Stakeholder Involvement: Networks and System Synergies

The architectural design of the course was the first outcome of the co-creation process, actively involving institutional partners (AOU Meyer, USR Toscana, Andrea Bocelli Foundation) and the participants themselves. The definition of the HCL's formative and research architecture stemmed from a complex process of negotiation and synthesis that saw the convergence of the scientific demands of the FORLILPSI Department with the operational needs expressed by strategic partners. This multi-actor approach ensured that objectives, content, and methodologies were not confined to a purely academic dimension but were firmly anchored to the reality of pediatric care contexts and responded to concrete needs felt by professionals in the field.

The selection of themes, while maintaining a predominant pedagogical matrix, followed a principle of multidisciplinary, articulating into a progressive pathway that moves from the micro-level of the care relationship (focusing on autobiographical methodologies and narrative medicine) to the meso-level of inclusive didactic design (focused on technology and evaluation), and finally to the macro-level of organizational ecology (dedicated to systemic analysis and leadership in healthcare contexts). The methodological framework was the most fertile ground for co-creation. Embracing the Mixed Methods Research (MMR) and Action Research paradigm, the project adopted an approach oriented towards reflective and transformative learning (Schön, 1993; Mezirow, 2016). The Course's teaching was

structured in a blended modality, alternating synchronous online lectures with in-person experiential workshops, combining the accessibility of distance learning with the irreplaceable value of direct interaction and the construction of a Community of Practice (Wenger, McDermott & Snyder, 2002). A key methodological element was the systematic use of E-tivities at the end of each module, acting not as simple exercises but as genuine devices for self-reflective learning and the production of qualitative data for research.

Concurrently, the dissemination of results and practices developed within the HCL was conceived not as a final project appendix but as a strategic and transversal activity, intrinsically linked to the co-creation phase. The goal was not merely to "communicate" results to a passive audience but to create opportunities for dialogue, exchange, and synergy to amplify the project's impact and foster the model's transferability. One primary strategy was the co-organization of scientific and training events in close collaboration with institutional partners (USR Toscana and AOU Meyer), which served the dual purpose of sharing research outcomes and strengthening the academic-scientific network. Finally, dissemination was realized through the building of national and international synergies, such as the comparative study with the Spanish system and the involvement of stakeholders at the national (e.g., Fondazione Gemelli IRCCS, USR Piemonte) and European levels (experiences from France, Spain, Austria), positioning the project as a reference point in the field of hospital pedagogy.

4.2.2 The Voice of Participants: Evidence from the Evaluation Questionnaire

An emblematic example of the iterative and participatory nature of the co-creative process is the re-modulation of the teaching calendar between the first (A.Y. 2022-2023) and second (A.Y. 2023-2024) editions of the Advanced Course. This redesign was not the result of a unilateral decision by the scientific committee but a direct and considered response to the training needs that emerged from the systematic monitoring of the first edition. The collected feedback clearly highlighted a specific criticality: the training load, particularly the high number of in-person meetings, proved difficult to sustain for participants primarily composed of professionals already burdened by intense work commitments. Fully consistent with the HCL's human-centered approach, the scientific directorate embraced this feedback as valuable research data and an opportunity for improvement. The re-modulation process thus involved a revision of the schedule to optimize the balance between distance and in-person activities, providing a reduced number of in-person meetings to alleviate the logistical and temporal burden on participants without sacrificing the quality of interaction.

4.2.3 Evaluative Phase: "We Will Lead the Fifth Module!" as a Collaborative Evaluation and Learning Experience

The activity "We Will Lead the Fifth Module!" ("Il quinto modulo lo facciamo noi!") exemplifies the co-creative philosophy and the action-research methodological approach driving the HCL. Proposed as the final E-tivity of Module IV of the 2023-2024 Advanced Course, this workshop was a genuine experience of simulated co-design. Participants, divided into small working groups, were tasked with designing a hypothetical fifth training module,

supplementary to the content already covered, with the aim of further improving the course's outputs. This methodological device had a dual and synergistic function:

- **Pedagogical Perspective:** It represented the culmination of an empowerment-oriented pathway. Participants were viewed not as passive recipients of prefabricated knowledge but as reflective professionals and competent actors, capable of critically analyzing their training experience and formulating proposals for improvement.
- **Research Perspective:** The workshop proved to be an invaluable source of qualitative data. The analysis of the group processes and the proposed topics provided direct insights into the most urgent perceived training needs. Valuable indications emerged, such as the need for greater depth on content related to design and co-design and, as already mentioned, the desire for a more structured training pathway. These findings directly informed both the redesign of the subsequent course edition and the launch of a First-Level Master's program.

4.2.4 Launch of the First-Level Master's Program 2025-2026

The most significant and tangible result of the co-creative process is undoubtedly the evolution of the Advanced Course into a First-Level University Master's Program, scheduled to commence in the academic year 2025-2026. This transformation was a direct response to a strong demand for greater professionalization expressed by the participants themselves, both through the evaluation questionnaires and, explicitly, during the "We Will Lead the Fifth Module!" co-design activity. The request from the course participants for a more structured and in-depth training pathway was thus adopted as a project mandate. The drafting of the Master's proposal, which took place between December 2024 and April 2025, was itself an exercise in extended co-design, actively involving institutional partners. Through a series of dedicated meetings, the proposal was developed in collaboration with the AOU Meyer and the USR Toscana. This shared journey ensured that the new Master's program responded to a dual need: on one hand, offering a more structured pathway that could include opportunities for professional traineeships; on the other, elevating the status of the training pathway, formally recognizing the transdisciplinarity of this professional area at the academic level. The Master's project was subsequently approved by the FORLILPSI Department Council on March 19, 2025, attesting to an institutionally validated process.

4.2.5 Research "Emotional Dimensions in Socio-Healthcare Organizational Contexts"

The integration of the research "Emotional dimensions in socio-healthcare organizational contexts," conducted by Prof. AnnaMaria Di Fabio, within the Advanced Course is another key outcome of the co-creative process. This initiative allowed for the experimentation of an innovative approach to training, where the learning pathway itself becomes a research setting, and participants transform into co-researchers of their own professional and emotional experience. The methodology involved administering targeted questionnaires in the initial and final stages of the course, aimed at understanding the emotional-motivational component within participants' professional and life paths. The value of this initiative transcends mere data collection. The act of responding to the questionnaires functioned as a powerful self-reflectivity and autobiography device, stimulating greater self-awareness and

understanding of one's professional presence. The integration of this research thus enriched the training pathway on multiple levels: it provided the research group with valuable data to assess the course's profound impact, equipped participants with a structured opportunity for personal and professional reflection, and validated the assumption that high-quality training must include the "care of the caregiver," valuing the emotional dimension as an essential component of professional competence.

5. Evaluation Results

Evaluation, within the action-research design that forms the backbone of the Health Community Lab (HCL), was conceived as an organic, recursive, and systematic process aimed at generating a vital and continuous feedback loop between the formative action and its reception by the participants. Fully consistent with the evidence-based approach that informed the entire project, the evaluation pursued a dual and synergistic strategic purpose: firstly, to provide a solid base of empirical evidence for the ongoing monitoring of the Advanced Course, rigorously identifying strengths and critical areas, and promptly guiding subsequent redesign phases towards continuous improvement; secondly, to collect and analyze qualitative and quantitative data on the transformative impact of the pathway, in order to validate the proposed pedagogical model and deeply understand its multiple and complex repercussions on participants' practice, awareness, and professional identity.

Key Indicators	Quantitative and Qualitative Results
<i>Number of Editions Held</i>	3 (Anni 2023, 2024, 2025)
<i>Number of Participants Trained</i>	105 (including 81 professionals and 24 university students)
<i>Number of Questionnaires Collected</i>	243 (administered for the evaluation of each of the 4 training modules)
<i>Average Satisfaction Rate</i>	91.04%.
<i>Perceived Transformative Impact Outcomes</i>	<p>Qualitative analysis validated the model as a transformative learning experience. Key outcomes include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Change of perspective: Participants report a "change of gaze" and a "new awareness" of their profession, describing "personal as well as professional growth." -Transferability of skills: A proven ability to transfer learnings into daily practice emerged. -Systemic impact: A shift was recorded from the application of single tools to genuine systemic and project-based interventions (e.g., multidisciplinary team meetings, professional autobiographical workshops). -Empowerment and Leadership: The action-research path triggered the development of a "diffuse pedagogical leadership" and a tangible process of professional empowerment.

Table 6 - Qualitative and Quantitative Results of the Key Indicators

The evaluation methodology adopted a Mixed Methods Research approach, integrating the administration of structured questionnaires at the end of each module with the analysis of narrative and autobiographical products realized during the E-tivities. The design of the

questionnaires, as detailed in the methodology chapter, leveraged the rigorous scientific framework of the national TECO-D Pedagogy project promoted by ANVUR (National Agency for the Evaluation of the University and Research System), ensuring the relevance, validity, and comparability of the indicators used to measure the achievement of learning objectives. This section aims to analytically illustrate and discuss the results emerging from this complex evaluative process, adopting a comparative perspective that contrasts data from the three editions of the Advanced Course (A.Y. 2022-2023, 2023-2024, and 2024-2025). The objective is to move beyond a simple static snapshot, instead reconstructing the evolutionary trajectory of the training pathway, demonstrating how the virtuous cycle of action, reflection, and redesign has allowed for the progressive refinement and enhancement of the offering. The discussion will be articulated into two macro-sections: the first dedicated to the comparative quantitative analysis of satisfaction and perceived impact, the second focused on the qualitative analysis of participant narratives. The integration of these two analytical lenses will provide a holistic and multidimensional picture of the formative experience and its outcomes, revealing not only what was learned but also how and why this learning proved significant and transformative for the professionals involved.

5.1 Comparative Quantitative Analysis: Trends and Variations in Satisfaction and Perceived Impact

The quantitative analysis of data collected through evaluation questionnaires offers an objective and systematic basis for comparing the different course editions and mapping trends related to participants' perceptions. This analysis allows for the measurement of satisfaction levels, the identification of thematic areas with the greatest impact, and the assessment of the pathway's professional fallout, highlighting constants and evolutions over time.

A first macroscopic finding that emerges with unequivocal clarity from the comparative analysis is the exceptionally high and constant level of satisfaction manifested by participants across all three editions. When questioned on the extent to which each module met their training needs and initial expectations, the overwhelming majority of respondents provided a fully positive evaluation. The comparative analysis reveals an interesting trend of progressive consolidation of this consensus, suggesting the effectiveness of the calibration and redesign process implemented between editions.

As illustrated in Matrix 5, the 2022-2023 edition, while already registering very high satisfaction levels, showed greater variability and a minority share of partial satisfaction. Starting from the 2023-2024 edition, following the re-modulation of the calendar and the reduction of in-person meetings (a decision made precisely based on the feedback from the first edition), a sharp increase in the percentages of full satisfaction is observed, which remain at excellent levels in the 2024-2025 edition as well. Module III, in particular, emerges in both of the latter two editions as a moment of peak appreciation, achieving an exceptional 100% full satisfaction in 2023-2024 and 2024-2025. These data, in their progression, not only attest to the intrinsic quality of the formative proposal but empirically demonstrate the effectiveness of the action-research cycle: systematic listening to participants and subsequent design action have yielded a measurable improvement in course perception.

The total absence of negative evaluations ("No" responses) across all surveys constitutes a further, powerful confirmation of the overall validity of the pedagogical model.

The comparative analysis of the topics perceived as most thoroughly covered reveals a notable coherence over time, testifying to the solidity and clarity of the course's pedagogical framework. In all editions, the dimensions related to relational, reflective, and methodological competencies emerge as the main area of perceived learning, validating the design intention to focus the pathway on transversal skills rather than on merely factual content.

As highlighted in Matrix 6, the theme of "Relational and Situational Dynamics" is confirmed, year after year and module after module, as the area of greatest impact, indicated by consistently very high percentages of participants. This data is of fundamental importance: it attests that the course successfully addresses the primary training need of professionals operating in care contexts, namely the necessity to acquire tools for managing the complexity of human interactions in situations of vulnerability. Alongside this constant, the persistent relevance of "Methods and Techniques for the Development and Facilitation of Learning Processes" and "Research Methodology" is observed, indicating that participants appreciate and recognize the value of an approach that equips them with a solid professional "toolbox" and the stance of a "researcher professional."

The predominant emergence of the theme of "Design Models" in Module IV shows how the course successfully guides participants through an evolutionary pathway that, starting from basic relational competencies, leads them towards the acquisition of more complex and strategic design and organizational competencies.

A crucial indicator of the effectiveness of an advanced training program lies in its ability to translate into a concrete enrichment of professional practice. The comparative analysis of data on this front is particularly telling and shows a clear growth trend regarding the actual application of what was learned in daily work. This data, more than any other, demonstrates the course's effectiveness in building a solid bridge between theory and practice.

<i>Module</i>	<i>2022-2023</i>	<i>2023-2024</i>	<i>2024-2025</i>	<i>Analysis of Variation</i>
Module I	95% / 5%	95,2% 4,8%	95,3,1% 4,7%	Stability at very high levels of satisfaction from the first module of the most recent editions.
Module II	85,7% 14,6%	86,4% 13,6%	83,3% 16,7%	Consolidation of appreciation, with a stable level of full satisfaction across the two most recent editions.

Module III	94,4% / 5,6%	100% 0%	100% 0%	The module reaches a peak in appreciation in both recent editions, indicating a particularly successful phase of the pathway that meets expectations.
Module IV	84,2% / 15,8%	91,7% 8,3%	85,5% 14,5%	Maintains an excellent level, concluding a pathway perceived as consistently positive.

Table 7 - Comparative Analysis of General Satisfaction by Module and Academic Year (% of "Yes" / "Only in part" responses)

<i>Formative Objective (TeCOD)</i>	<i>2022-2023 Edition (Average)</i>	<i>2022-2023 Edition (Average)</i>	<i>2022-2023 Edition (Average)</i>	<i>Analysis of Variation and Constants</i>
Relational and Situational Dynamics	81%	70%	68%	Confirmed across all editions as by far the most relevant topic, attesting to the centrality of the relational dimension in the pathway.
Methods and Techniques for Learning	45,5%	50%	49%	Consistently maintains a position of importance, indicating appreciation for the operational tools provided.
Research Methodology	45%	45%	48%	Slight growth in the latest edition suggests increasing interest in the approach of the reflective and research-oriented professional.

Design Models	83,3%	65%	70%	Its prominence in the final module indicates the culmination of a pathway that develops advanced design competencies
Constructs and Theories	51%	35%	33%	Indicates that, while appreciated, the purely theoretical dimension is perceived as less impactful than the methodological and relational ones.
Organizational Management	9,6%	15%	15%	Less frequently selected, but its presence indicates the introduction of a systemic and organizational vision of the profession.

Table 8 - Comparative Analysis of Areas with Greatest Impact (% of participants who selected the topic)

The evaluation of the professional utility of the individual teachings has consistently remained at excellent levels across all editions, with average scores very close to the maximum on the scale. However, it is in the comparison of applicability that the most interesting evolution is captured. As shown in Table 9, the percentage of participants who report having already applied their learning in their professional practice shows a growing trend, both within the same edition (from the first to the later modules) and across the different editions. This suggests that the progressive re-modulations of the course, with an increasing emphasis on the laboratory dimension and the production of concrete E-tivities, have had a direct and measurable effect on participants' ability to transfer acquired competencies to their work context. The shift from a more contained initial application to percentages that, in the final modules of the latest editions, well exceed 80%, testifies to the success of a pedagogical model that is not satisfied with "teaching" but aims to "enable" action.

<i>Module</i>	<i>2022-2023</i>	<i>2023-2024</i>	<i>2024-2025</i>	<i>Analysis of Variation</i>
Module I	76,2%	76,2%	63%	Stability of the initial data, reflecting a theoretical assimilation phase
Module II	57,1%	77,3%	85,7%	Sharp increase indicating the start of competency transfer. Stability across editions.
Module III	61,3%	81,3%	85,7%	Peak applicability, coinciding with the phase of greatest mastery and awareness. Stability at excellent levels.
Module IV	62,2%	66,7%	66,7%	Consolidation of application, though slightly lower than the Module III peak.

Table 9 - Comparative Analysis of Practical Applicability (% of "Yes" responses)

5.2 Comparative Qualitative Analysis of Narratives: Voices, Meanings, and Transformative Learning Processes

While quantitative analysis provides the statistical skeleton of the evaluation, it is the qualitative analysis of open comments, motivations, and concluding reflections that conveys its soul, allowing access to the richness of subjective meanings and the transformative processes triggered by the pathway. The comparative analysis of narratives collected across the different editions offers a deep and nuanced understanding of the course's impact, bringing forth constants, evolutions, and, crucially, concrete evidence of the change that occurred in participants' practice and professional identity.

Three main strengths consistently emerge from the qualitative analysis: The first is the high competence and sensitivity of the instructors. Comments constantly praise the "clarity, delicacy, and sensitivity" with which complex themes were addressed, and the trainers' ability to combine scientific rigor with profound humanity. One participant describes the content as "excellent" and the instructors as "expert and prepared." The second strength is the reflective and autobiographical methodological approach. Narrative-based activities and the analysis of one's professional history were universally appreciated as a powerful learning tool. "I greatly appreciated [...] the autobiographical activity, in fact, I was able to contribute

more actively," writes one course participant, highlighting how this approach fosters engagement and personalized learning. The third pillar is the laboratory and community dimension. Group work, both online and in-person, was perceived as a fundamental added value. "I highly appreciate the ongoing activities that allow comparison with other course participants," comments one participant, underscoring how peer interaction fostered the construction of a "Community of Practice" and mutual enrichment.

A theme that emerges with overwhelming and constant force across all editions is the transformative dimension of the formative experience, in full alignment with the Mezirow paradigm. Year after year, participants' comments are not limited to expressing mere satisfaction but describe a true shift in perspective, a "personal and professional growth." Narratives from the first edition, though positive, were perhaps more focused on acquiring "new points for reflection." In subsequent editions, a greater depth and awareness are observed in describing this change. Comments from the 2024-2025 edition, for example, explicitly mention a "change in outlook" on one's profession, the ability to "read complexity," and an increased "awareness of one's role." A participant from the latest edition writes: "This course didn't just give me tools; it changed the way I think about my work and myself as a professional." This evolution in language suggests that the course, over time, has become increasingly effective in triggering not only first-level learning (knowledge acquisition) but also second-level learning (critical review of one's frames of reference). The constant mention of "self-care" as a fundamental discovery ("I learned to take care of others by taking care of myself") indicates that the pathway succeeds in touching deep chords of personal and professional identity, generating an impact that extends far beyond the workplace.

The comparative analysis of perceived strengths reveals an interesting evolution. In all editions, two constants emerge clearly: the high competence and sensitivity of the instructors and the effectiveness of the reflective and autobiographical methodological approach. However, while the emphasis in the first edition was primarily on the quality of individual training interventions, a third pillar emerges with increasing force in subsequent editions: the communal and laboratory dimension. Comments from the 2023-2024 and 2024-2025 editions specifically praise the "group atmosphere," the "peer comparison," and the "richness of exchange between different professionals." One participant writes: "The most valuable thing I'm taking home is the network of colleagues I've met and hope to continue collaborating with." This evolution indicates that the course has successfully transformed from a series of excellent seminars into an authentic "Community of Practice," a result that is a direct consequence of the progressive emphasis placed on group work, in-person workshops, and co-design activities.

The comparative analysis of critical issues is perhaps the most powerful indicator of the effectiveness of the action-research cycle. The main criticism from the first edition (2022-2023) concerned the excessive density of the calendar and the burden of in-person meetings. As previously highlighted, this criticism was embraced and led to a significant course re-modulation. The fact that this complaint almost completely disappears in subsequent editions, where the blended modality is even praised as a strength, demonstrates that the evaluation and redesign process has worked. In the most recent editions, a more "mature" criticism emerges: no longer an organizational complaint, but a request for greater depth, for "even more concrete examples," and for a "greater anchoring to daily practice." This request, far from being a sign of weakness, should be interpreted as

an indicator of the course's success: it is precisely the most engaged and stimulated participants who wish to delve deeper and translate every theoretical concept into professional action. This evolution in the nature of the criticisms is a sign of the growth of the group's "formative capital."

Finally, the comparative analysis of practical applications shows a clear expansion and increasing complexity of the innovations introduced by participants in their work. While initial applications were more limited to the introduction of single narrative tools (e.g., "I used a picture book in class"), more recent narratives describe more complex and systemic interventions. Participants from the latest edition speak of "having restructured the morning reception time according to a narrative approach," of "having introduced multidisciplinary team meetings for drafting personalized educational projects based on the course model," and of "having launched an autobiographical writing project with colleagues to improve the ward climate." This shift from an instrumental application to a systemic and project-based application is the most eloquent proof of the course's success in promoting not only technical competencies but also and above all a diffuse pedagogical leadership, capable of generating an impact not just on individual practice but on the entire organizational context.

These competencies manifest through specific requests emerging from participants during the critical feedback and design phase. Among these, the necessity to integrate frontal lessons with laboratory activities is emphasized, in line with Dewey's active school pedagogy (1899), to maximize involvement. The need to give more space to the "restitution" of group work and comparison (such as clinical journal analysis) is also requested, even at the expense of some frontal intervention, valuing "peer education" and the importance of poster presentations. These solicitations confirm the effectiveness of the communal and laboratory dimension.

Finally, the requests raise issues of extraordinary ethical-professional and systemic relevance. Firstly, it is suggested to include dedicated reflection spaces on how professionals address the suffering and possible death of pupils/patients—a theme that profoundly affects the identity of the teacher and healthcare worker. Secondly, the systemic problem of care for "siblings" (brothers and sisters) of individuals in situations of illness and/or disability strongly emerges, as they often bear the burden of guilt and family neglect, with lasting repercussions on their lives. These suggestions, requiring greater anchoring to practice and reflection on extreme and complex themes, confirm the trend toward the systemic and project-based application of acquired competencies, as demonstrated by the shift in narratives from the use of single tools to the introduction of multidisciplinary team meetings and autobiographical writing projects among colleagues to improve the organizational climate, highlighting the birth of a diffuse pedagogical leadership.

In conclusion, the results of the evaluation process, analyzed from a comparative perspective, yield the image of a training project that is alive, dynamic, and constantly evolving. The integrated analysis of quantitative and qualitative data not only validates the relevance and effectiveness of the pedagogical and methodological approach of the Health Community Lab but also illuminates the process through which the Course has grown and refined itself over time, thanks to attentive and systematic listening to the voices of its protagonists. These results provide a solid evidence base to support the future evolution of the project, starting with the transformation of the Advanced Course into a First-Level

University Master's Program, with the awareness of having built not only a training offer of excellence but a genuine community of reflective professionals, agents of change in the delicate and valuable world of care.

6. Concluding Reflections

The three-year action-research journey of the Health Community Lab (HCL), having reached its moment of synthesis and prospective relaunch, is configured not as an endpoint but as a fundamental stage in a broader heuristic and transformative process. Born from the deeply felt need in the clinical and academic context to overcome a sectoral and ancillary conception of pedagogy in healthcare settings, the project set the ambitious goal of investigating, promoting, and validating a model for the systemic integration of the pedagogical-educational dimension within the pediatric care continuum. These concluding reflections aim to critically retrace the path taken, bringing the results from the different phases of investigation and intervention into dialogue, in order to distill not only the scientific evidence produced but also the epistemological, methodological, and policy implications arising from them. The integrated analysis of quantitative and qualitative data, professional narratives, and co-creative processes allows us to state with reasonable certainty that the HCL has not merely implemented a successful training initiative but has acted as a genuine laboratory for social and organizational innovation. It has triggered a process of individual and collective empowerment, contributed to consolidating the identity of a community of reflective practices, and laid the foundations for a structural rethinking of the role of education within healthcare cultures and organizations. The most significant outcome of the project, therefore, does not lie in a single product or a numerical datum, however flattering, but in the validation of an approach—an operational model based on the synergy between research, training, and intervention, capable of generating sustainable change because it is co-constructed with the actors of the context themselves.

6.1. *Empirical Validation of a Transformative Training Model*

The most significant innovation stemming from the HCL project lies not merely in its content or its impact on individuals, but rather in the invention and validation of a veritable "integrated training pipeline" for learning within the pediatric hospital setting. This model, which represents the practical application of the HCL approach to the context of hospital and home-bound education, is structured across several interconnected levels:

- The integration of training pathways: The model establishes a continuum linking internships (for university students), advanced university training (the Advanced Training Course), and continuous professional development (for in-service professionals), thereby ensuring coherence and the progressive development of professional expertise.
- The development of integrated competencies: This pipeline is designed to cultivate a set of context-specific competencies, transcending the traditional dichotomy between technical expertise and humanistic knowledge. Crucial emphasis is placed not only on disciplinary competencies but also, and preeminently, on relational-communicative competencies (e.g., conflict management, active listening, mediation) and organizational-managerial competencies (e.g., project design, pedagogical leadership, interprofessional teamwork).
- A holistic and ecosystemic approach: The HCL model has been demonstrated to operate within an ecosystemic context (hospital-school-university-family-community). Within this system, all components are coordinated by a "pedagogical flywheel",

which functions as the driving force and organizing principle, applying a coherent educational vision across all educational and training pathways.

- Social innovation as a collective outcome: The most significant outcome of this HCL approach, when applied in practice, is the social innovation it has generated. This innovation was not a top-down imposition; rather, it is the result of the training and active participation of all members involved in the Advanced Training Course, the internships, and the subsequent related events. The very process of collaborative training emerged as the primary driver of organizational and cultural change.

The HCL presented, the Advanced Course "The School in Hospital," was conceived from the outset as a transformative learning environment, a "construction site" where professionals could critically deconstruct and reconstruct their implicit theories and professional practices. The results of the continuous evaluation process, analyzed from a comparative perspective across the three editions, provide robust and multidimensional empirical validation of the model's effectiveness.

The quantitative analysis yielded a picture of exceptionally high and progressively consolidating satisfaction, a datum which, despite its apparent simplicity, indicates a profound alignment between the training proposal and the participants' real needs. The increasing trend in levels of full satisfaction, which reached peaks of over 90% and even 100% in the latest editions, demonstrates the effectiveness of the virtuous action-research cycle: systematic listening to feedback and the consequent re-modulation of the schedule and workload produced a measurable and perceived improvement. Even more significant is the consistency with which, year after year, participants identified "Relational and Situational Dynamics" and "Methods and Techniques for Learning Facilitation" as the areas of greatest formative impact. This constant is not coincidental: it attests to the course's success in focusing on the transversal, reflective, and methodological competencies that constitute the true core of educational professionalism in highly complex settings. The course was perceived not as a disciplinary update but as a pathway for enhancing one's "way of being" and "way of doing" in the care relationship.

However, it is the qualitative analysis of participant narratives that reveals the deeper scope of the course's impact. The voices of professionals describe a genuine process of transformation. The key words that recur with persistent frequency—"change in outlook," "new awareness," "profound reflection," "personal as well as professional growth"—are indicators of learning that affected not only the repertoire of skills but also the meaning schemes, sense-making perspectives, and the very identity of the participants. The shift from a conception of pedagogy as a "set of techniques" to an understanding of pedagogy as an "existential posture" and a "key for interpreting complexity" represents perhaps the most valuable formative outcome. The narratives highlight how the methodological approach based on reflectivity, autobiography, and narration was not just a "content" of the course but its living "method," the device that allowed participants to directly experience generative and not merely reproductive learning. As one course participant stated, "this course didn't just give me tools; it changed the way I think about my work and myself as a professional," a perfect synthesis of a process that successfully integrated the cognitive dimension with the emotional and identity dimensions.

The ultimate proof of this transformation lies in the participants' extraordinary capacity to transfer their learning to daily practice. The growing trend in applicability, which consistently exceeded 80% in the final phases of the pathway, and the richness of the concrete examples reported in the narratives—from the introduction of the narrative clinical journal to the restructuring of entire ward routines, from experimenting with autobiographical writing workshops with colleagues to initiating new interprofessional collaborations—demonstrate that the course successfully built a solid and well-trafficked bridge between the training room and the professional field. This result refutes the tired accusation of abstractness often directed at academic training and validates a pedagogical model that, precisely because it is based on reflection stemming from experience, proves eminently practical and generative of innovation.

Beyond individual impact, one of the most significant and sustainable outcomes of the HCL project has been the progressive crystallization of a community of reflective practices. The co-creative methodology acted as a powerful social catalyst, transforming a heterogeneous group of professionals into a cohesive network, based on the sharing of a language, a horizon of meaning, and a common commitment. The analysis of the modules co-designed by the participants not only provided valuable insights for the future of the course but also unveiled the profile of a mature, conscious, and proactive professional community.

The requests that emerged—greater anchoring to immersive practice, in-depth study of complex relational competencies (including intercultural mediation), greater attention to "care for the caregiver," and, above all, a growing interest in the organizational and pedagogical leadership dimension—are not mere "wish lists" but the distinctive features of a professional identity that has moved beyond a purely executive view of its role. Participants did not ask for "recipes" or prefabricated "techniques" but manifested a need for agency, critical thinking, and strategic competencies to act as agents of change within their contexts. This shift from a demand for training as a product to a demand for empowerment is the most tangible sign of the success of an approach that treated professionals not as vessels to be filled but as co-researchers and active constructors of their own knowledge.

6.2. Epistemological and Policy Implications: Pedagogy as Strategic Knowledge for the Humanization of Care

The results of the HCL project, in their entirety, transcend the specific scope of training to raise broader epistemological and policy issues. The project, as a whole, can be read as a "case study" that empirically demonstrates the thesis that pedagogy, when correctly understood and implemented, is not an accessory or "side" discipline relative to medical knowledge, but strategic, critical, and transformative knowledge, indispensable for the humanization of care contexts.

At the epistemological level, the HCL experience contributes to the debate on the status of Hospital Pedagogy, supporting a vision of this discipline not as a simple technical sub-sector but as an intrinsically interstitial, heterotopian, and boundary field of knowledge. The practice of the pedagogue in the hospital, as emerged from the research and training, is not limited to "applying" pedagogical theories but generates new, hybrid knowledge that arises precisely from critical dialogue and contamination with medical, psychological, and organizational

knowledge. The HCL demonstrated how it is possible to overcome the historical "power asymmetry" between the hegemonic medical discourse and the pedagogical one, not through a claim for sterile autonomy but through the construction of a synergistic and transdisciplinary collaboration. The pedagogue does not propose an alternative to the physician but as an ally who brings a different but complementary interpretative lens and operational competence, focused on the whole person, the quality of relationships, learning processes, and the construction of meaning during the experience itself.

This perspective has profound policy and organizational implications. If the pedagogical dimension is constitutive of a truly holistic care process, then it cannot be delegated to sporadic interventions or single professional figures but must become an ordering principle for the entire healthcare organization. The hospital must evolve from a "place for the provision of services" to a "learning and care ecosystem," a community where every actor—from physician to volunteer, from parent to administrative staff—is aware of the educational value of their actions. This requires deep cultural change and the introduction of coherent organizational devices, such as the provision of pedagogical leadership figures at the systemic level, the integration of educational quality indicators into evaluation processes, and systematic investment in the interprofessional training of all caregivers. The success of the HCL model, founded on a solid partnership between the University, Hospital, School Office, and Third Sector, demonstrates that this transformation is possible, but requires a clear policy vision and the construction of strategic alliances.

6.3 Research Limitations and Future Perspectives: Towards Model Systematization

A critical and honest analysis cannot exempt itself from acknowledging the inherent limitations of the present study. The nature of the project, configured as an exploratory multiple case study, while ensuring great depth of analysis, does not allow for statistical generalizations. The results are deeply tied to the specificity of the AOU Meyer context, an area of excellence that may not be representative of the average reality of the national and international healthcare landscape. Furthermore, the evaluation of the formative impact is largely based on participant perception and would require further longitudinal studies to objectively measure the change in professional practices and its effects on care outcomes for patients and families. However, these limitations do not invalidate the proposed model but, on the contrary, clearly outline the directions for future development. The evidence gathered is sufficiently robust and coherent to support the need to move from an experimentation phase to a phase of systematization and dissemination of the HCL model.

The most immediate and concrete perspective is the transformation of the Advanced Course into a First-Level University Master's Program, starting from the academic year 2025-2026. This evolution, a direct consequence of the course's success and the demand from the professional community, represents a crucial step in providing a stable and recognized academic home for the training of the highly complex hospital pedagogue profile that the project has helped to delineate.

Future research directions must focus on broadening the field of investigation, including a greater variety of healthcare contexts (general hospitals, territorial services, palliative care) and delving into specific themes that emerged as particularly relevant, such as inclusion, intercultural mediation, parental support in chronic illness situations, and the evaluation of

the impact of educational interventions on child well-being indicators. It will also be essential to develop action-research projects aimed at experimenting with and validating models of diffuse pedagogical leadership within healthcare organizations, in order to translate the principles discussed here into concrete process and system innovations.

The Health Community Lab has offered a significant contribution, both scientifically and in terms of professional practice, to the redefinition of the relationship between pedagogy and care. It has demonstrated that investing in pedagogical competence is not an additional "cost" to the healthcare system but a fundamental strategic investment to improve the quality, effectiveness, and humanity of pediatric assistance.

The path outlined is still long and complex, but the foundations laid are solid. The future challenge will be to cultivate and grow the community of practices that has been generated, to disseminate the culture and methodologies experimented with, and to continue working, through the synergy between rigorous research and transformative action, for a future where every place of care can also be, and above all, a place of life, growth, and learning.

The Future of HCL

HCLs are created to activate shared and sustainable innovation processes, in which the community and stakeholders become protagonists. Their purpose is not to co-create temporary solutions, but to leave the responsibility and capacity to carry them forward over time in the hands of the community. Each HCL therefore aims to build autonomy and collective *agency*, encouraging the creation of local networks capable of sustaining and regenerating the change produced.

To ensure that these local experiences do not remain isolated initiatives but become structural policies and stable tools for innovation in the regional healthcare system, a further step is necessary: the creation of *the Health Community Hub* (HC HUB).

The HC HUB represents the evolutionary perspective of HCLs: a regional platform for coordination, learning and enhancement, capable of ensuring methodological consistency, disseminating and replicating innovations, and integrating results into healthcare system policies and services. Without such an institutional and political framework, HCLs would risk remaining episodic experiments, whereas their potential is to become permanent drivers of systemic innovation, serving the health and well-being of Tuscan communities.

Bibliography

Anvur. Agenzia Nazionale di Valutazione del sistema Universitario e della Ricerca. (2017). *Definizione dei saperi minimi* (TECO-D). Roma.

Baldacci, M. (2004). *Modelli della didattica*. Carocci.

Betti, E., Biggeri M. et al. (2023). *Health Community Lab. Le Linee Guida per la realizzazione*. Università degli Studi di Firenze.

Biggeri M., Betti E., Boffo V., Bonaccorsi G., Caruso E., Gallo P., Lingua V., Menicagli D., Setola N. (2025) *Health Community Lab: un modello di co-creazione per l'innovazione sociale e sanitaria in Toscana*. Florence University Press. Florence.

Boffo, V. (2022). *La scuola in ospedale. Tirocinio e formazione degli insegnanti*. Editpress.

Boffo, V., Benelli, C. (2024). *Teorie, metodologie e pratiche della ricerca autobiografica per le professioni educative, scolastiche, culturali e di cura*. Anthology Digital Publishing.

Boffo, V., Togni, F. (2023). Cura di sé, cura dell'altro, cura del mondo: l'esperienza della cura educativa per il corpo dell'adulto. In Morandi, M., (Ed.), *Dieci lezioni di pedagogia per le scienze motorie*, pp- 73-91. Utet Universitaria.

Bronfenbrenner, U. (2002). *Ecologia dello sviluppo umano*. Il Mulino. (ed.Orig. 1979).

Cambi, F. (2002). *L'autobiografia come metodo formativo*. Laterza.

Castoldi M. (2011). *Progettare per competenze. Percorsi e strumenti*. Carocci.

Creswell, J. W., & Clark, V. L. P. (2018). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*, 3rd ed, Sage publications.

Del Gobbo, G. (2018). Approccio olistico tra ricerca e azione educativa. Riflessioni introduttive. In Federighi, P., (Ed.), *Educazione in età adulta Ricerche, politiche, luoghi e professioni* (pp. 112-122).FUP.

Demetrio, D. (1996). *Raccontarsi. L'autobiografia come cura di sé*. Raffaello Cortina Editore.

Dewey, J. (1964). *Scuola e società*. La Nuova Italia. (ed.Orig. 1899).

European Association for Children in Hospital. (1993). *Carta di EACH*. <https://each-for-sick-children.org/>

Etzkowitz H., Leydesdorff L. (2000). The dynamics of innovation: from national systems and 'mode 2' to a triple helix of university-industry-government relations, *Research Policy*, Vol. 29, pp.109–123.

Federighi P. (2000). *Glossario dell'educazione degli adulti in Europa*, Associazione Europea dell'Educazione degli Adulti.

Galliani, L. (2015). *L'agire valutativo. Manuale per docenti e formatori*. Sei.

Hannan, M. T. & Freeman, J. (1989). *Organizational ecology*. Harvard University Press

Hospital Organisations of Pedagogues in Europe. (2000). *Carta di Hope*. Barcellona. <https://www.hospitalteachers.eu/who/hope-charter>

Mezirow, J. (2016). *La teoria dell'apprendimento trasformativo. Imparare a pensare come un adulto*. Raffaello Cortina.

Mortari L. (2006). *La pratica dell'aver cura*, Mondadori.

Organizzazione Mondiale della Sanità. (1948). *Costituzione*, Ginevra, p.1. Disponibile in: <https://apps.who.int/gb/gov/assets/constitution-en.pdf> (10/2025)

Organizzazione Nazioni Unite (1989). *Convenzione sui Diritti dell'Infanzia e dell'Adolescenza*. Ginevra: Onu.

Parlamento Europeo. (1986). *Carta europea dei bambini degenti in ospedale*. Risoluzione del Parlamento europeo A2-25/86, GUCE 13.5.1986, N.C 148/37. Unione Europea.

Schön, A. D. (1993). *Il professionista riflessivo. Per una nuova epistemologia della pratica professionale*. Dedalo.

Senge, P. M. (1990). *The fifth discipline: The art and practice of the learning organization*. Doubleday.

Siegel, D., & Hartzell, M. (2005). *Errori da non ripetere. Come la conoscenza della propria storia aiuta ad essere genitori*. Raffaello Cortina.

Trincherò, R. (2004). *I metodi della ricerca educativa*. Laterza.

Tronto, J. C. (1993). *Confini morali. Un argomento politico per l'etica della cura*. Diabasis (ed. 2006).

Wenger, E., McDermott, R., Snyder, W. (2002) *Cultivating Communities of Practice: A Guide to Managing Knowledge*. Harvard Business School Press.

World Health Organization (2016). *The Global strategy and action plan on ageing and health 2016–2020: towards a world in which everyone can live a long and healthy life*. ONU.

